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Usa International Open Conference 2024

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**COMPATIBILITY OF LITERATURE WITH THE
ADMINISTRATION SYSTEM AND ECONOMY IN THE WORKS OF
MUKIMI**

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Annotation: This article talks about the poems and ghazals of Muhammad Aminkhoja Mirzakhoja ugli Mukimi, the great poet and thinker of his time, the socio-economic situation of the 19th-20th centuries, and in addition, in these works, the state his attitude and critical thoughts towards the administration and the economy of his time were discussed and analyzed. In addition, the extent to which these critical comic masterpieces and ghazals of Mukimi influenced the state administration and economy is explained in detail.

Key words: Mukimi, his life and work, state administration, literature, economy, economic views, critical thoughts, politics, justice.

Introduction

Literature is the art of words. He strives to find subtle nuances and tones in the human heart and soul, and to reflect them through words. Samples of fiction that can reach the highest level represent the thoughts, experiences, and hopes that stir and excite humanity. Just as people in the world are not alike, so are their emotional experiences. The history of Uzbek literature is rich in masterpieces that skillfully reflect human mental states. They can arouse excitement in the minds and hearts of the current generation and contribute to their spiritual enrichment. Importantly, they are not limited to increasing our educational knowledge, but serve to improve our

artistic taste and spiritual maturity.

Muhammad Aminkhoja Mirzakhoja ugli, known by the nickname Mukimi, was born in Kokand in 1850 in a family of intellectuals. He was a witness of a period of social and political upheaval in a certain sense of political change in this area, that is, the region. We can see that the Uzbek poet and thinker was able to use satire and intelligence together to turn the problems of poverty, injustice, and corruption into a positive side, especially the political and economic situation, and turn it into a weapon against these problems.

Literature review

Mukimi's poems, enriched with the politics of his time, occupied a deep place in the hearts of the people and resonated with them. He criticized the government's oppressive actions against the people and was not afraid to speak openly about it. His cartoons such as "Maskovchi boy tarifida", "Veksel", "Viktor Boy" and "Tanobchilar" are cries for reforming society, expressing the pain of the oppressed and their frustration with this system of government.

Chiqib yangi maskovchidan boylar,

Sinar o'tmayin ba'zisin oylar.

These verses in the comic book "Tariff of the Muscovite Boy" after the accession of Central Asia to Russia, the beginning and development of capitalist relations caused the emergence of rich people who go to Moscow to trade, and this is what it is about.

Xususankim eshoni Xodixo'jam,

Yo'q og'zida qarzini vahmida nam.

Here Mukimi moves from universality to particularity, that is, it becomes clearer who this comic exposes. Khodikhoja Eshon was one of the rich people of Kokand at that time, he owned large cotton fields, cotton cleaning factories, stores, and

branches of these stores in other regions of Fergana. In addition to the comic strip "The Muscovite Boy on the Tariff", his character, who often mentions this person in his satires "Veksel", "Viktor Boy" and others, revealed new aspects of his character and was wrapped in satire to the public. presented in the case and exposed the class of exploiters, i.e. the class of property owners who use the property and labor of others, as a full representative.

**Der emishki, o'risga nisfin beray,
Kelar yilga yarmiga muhlat so'ray.
Qachon bo'lmagan gap qabul aylasin,
Muqarra degaykim, pechat boylasin.**

Since the revolution, there have been such agreements between borrowers and lenders, that is, if a person borrows money and cannot repay it within the agreed time period, that is, if he starts working at the expense of his business, his property is confiscated by the moneylenders as collateral, and they "printed" with l and appropriated. Mukimi is talking about this phenomenon that created capitalist relations.

**Netarmiz, debon qistamas el pulin,
–Berurmen, –desa, –so'miga o'n tiyin.**

In this satire, we will see these lines and all of us will be speechless from the usury and corruption of those times. The debtor was obliged to pay the specified amount (rate) of money rent as a bribe (usury) to the moneylender and officials. Usury flourished after the introduction of capitalist relations, resulting in increased indebtedness among the local working people. Responsibility is one of the main problems and themes of the literature of these times.

**Kelib qoldi o'ziga nogah qasam,
Sarih bo'ldi yolg'onligi muttaham.**

In those times, if he sued someone, the law, i.e. Sharia, made the plaintiff swear an oath to the responsible persons. This issue of oath was one of the worst and unbearable laws of that time. Rich people, big property owners, big landowners used to swear as a weapon to kill ordinary poor local people, many of them, and destroy peasants. That is, with various threats and pressures, they pledged their property worth several times more than their debts as collateral and swore that they would agree to confiscate them if they could not pay off their debts.

Results of research

It would not be an exaggeration to say that these criticisms, wrapped in the garb of open satire, are Mukimi's weapon against the politics of Tsarist Russia. Mukymi's comic books will not bore the reader. Sometimes it makes you laugh, and sometimes it makes you think deeply. The heroes of his comics are certainly not absent in our time. He was able to quickly enter the hearts of the people through his humorous stories. His simple, easy-to-understand comics reflect real-life events. In the hands of the poet, laughter is not rude laughter or just cheerfulness, small humor, but obstacles to backward progress in life, weaknesses and negative signs in the mind and nature of individuals, ugly character and inappropriate behavior. serves the function of condemnation, rebuke, warning.

Discussion

Mukimi's skillful use of images and metaphors adds depth and poignancy to his political commentary. He describes the suffering and the downtrodden in such a way that every person who reads these poems can stand against such injustices and, of course, fight against them, and feel the hardships of those times in spirit.

Moreover, the influence of Mukimi's poems went beyond the borders of Uzbekistan. His poems, ghazals, and humor have been translated into various languages, especially English, German, Russian, Bengali, and Hindi, and have reached literature lovers all over the world. Scholars and lovers of literature continue

to analyze his work, appreciating its historical content, social commentary and economic aspects, political appeal and purely artistic qualities. Koldosh Pardayev, Ghulam Karimov and Said Abdulla are among such enthusiasts.

At a time when Uzbekistan is trying to make its own way in the world literary scene, Mukimi's critical poems and ghazals remain a source of inspiration. His political poetry serves as a beacon that reminds us of the power of opposition and the importance of fighting for social justice.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we can say that the poems and ghazals he wrote down are not just writings, but they are an eternal mirror reflecting the constant struggle between oppression, tyranny, corruption and justice and solidarity. Although a century has passed since the creation of these masterpieces, his verses still retain their power and remind us that the struggle for justice and responsibility requires constant effort. As mentioned above, Mukimi's legacy serves as a beacon, that is, language and literature are used as weapons against lies and injustice. urges not to hesitate. Studying the way of life and creativity of this great person not only gives pleasure, but also cognitive knowledge and new knowledge. As a result of each re-search, other new aspects will emerge and ensure that we have the right attitude to justice and public policy of the youth.

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**Развитие устной и письменной речи на уроках русского как
иностранного**

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Аннотация

Актуальность проблемы обусловлена необходимостью изучения методики преподавания русского как иностранного на уровне устной и письменной речи и проблемы переноса теоретических знаний на практику, т.е. изучения на современном этапе.

Annotation

The relevance of the problem is due to the need to study the methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language at the level of oral and written speech and the problem of transferring theoretical knowledge to practice, i.e. studying at the present stage.

Ключевые слова: игровые методы, приёмы, инновационное обучение, метод обучения, интернет, методология, обучение, педагогика, русский язык как иностранный.

Keywords: game methods, techniques, innovative learning, teaching method, Internet, methodology, teaching, pedagogy, Russian as a foreign language.

В системе упражнений для обучения аудированию можно выделить две группы. Одна из них включает в себя упражнения, направленные на отработку

отдельных составляющих элементов деятельности. Такие упражнения развивают механизмы аудирования, фонетический и интонационный слух, вырабатывают навыки узнавания и дифференциации языковых единиц различных уровней, т.е. формируют фонетические, лексические и грамматические навыки аудирования. Т.к. они являются I ступенью, ведущей к формированию аудитивных умений, их определяют как подготовительные. Их также называют устно-языковыми, устно-тренировочными. Приведём некоторые примеры.

1. Прослушайте слова. Сравните гласные и согласные в парах. Повторите слова за учителем.

сено – сестра, семя – семья, дети – дела, джем – жена, шест – наше, шея – ваше, зал – глаз, замок – раз, дом – город, дело – тетрадь, голос – друг, жена – муж.

Посмотрите на транскрипцию, сопоставьте её со словами, которые вы только что прослушали.

[с'им'ја] [д'ила] [жына] [вашы] [горът] [друк] [муш] [глас]

2. Послушайте, как их произносит преподаватель. Познакомьтесь с их транскрипцией:

традиция – [тръд'ицы] ъ]

праздник – [праз'н'ик]

в праздник – [ф праз'н'ик]

Вторая группа – это речевые упражнения, которые по существу представляют собой управляемую речевую деятельность, т.к. обеспечивают практику аудирования на основе комплексного преодоления аудитивных трудностей.

С аудированием тесно связано говорение, как вид устной речевой деятельности. Обучение говорению также имеет свои специфические

особенности. При обучении диалогу различаются подготовительные (тренировочные) и речевые упражнения.

Наиболее простыми из подготовительных являются имитативные упражнения в виде вопросно-ответного единства (Это стол? – Да, это стол.). Потом: Это стол или стул? – Это стул. Сложнее – вопросы с вопросительным словом, т.к. вместо вопросительного слова нужно употребить слово в нужной форме (О чём мы говорим?).

На начальном этапе широко используются упражнения на продуцирование диалога с заранее оговорённым заданием и упражнения, вызванные стимулятором первой, опорной реплики. На этом же этапе выполняются подготовительные упражнения, обучающие реакции на лингвистический стимул. Например:

1. Отреагируйте на следующие высказывания:

а) – Очень приятно!

- ...

б) – Вам что-нибудь нужно?

- ...

г) – Где выход?

- ...

2. Дополните диалоги просьбой или вопросом:

а) - ...

- Можно ещё раз ваше имя?

б) - ...

- Да, мне нужно принять душ.

в) - ...

- Нет, завтрак не нужно. Чай, если можно.

Цель выполнения подготовительных упражнений – выработка речевых

автоматизмов, подготовка к спонтанной речи. Перенос речевых автоматизмов в естественное общение осуществляется через выполнение коммуникативных (речевых) упражнений.

1. Представьте, что вы пришли в гости к русской семье. Прочитайте диалог и разыграйте его.

2. Представьте, что вы в гостях.

а) Попросите хозяев показать дом, используя предложения с вопросительным словом „где?“

б) Попросите их дать вам что-нибудь, используя конструкции „можно мне“/„мне нужно“.

3. Вместе с партнёром обсудите ваши представления о „правильной“ рождестве, а также то, что вас удивило в рассказе о русских традициях празднования рождества.

Примеры упражнений для развития монологической речи:

1. Расскажите о своей семье (покажите фотографии, если они у тебя есть).

2. Используйте слова и выражения: здравствуйте, меня зовут...; я (студент); я (американец); у меня есть...; это...; его (её) зовут...; моя мама (мой папа)...

3. Выпишите все слова, которые, как вы думаете, характеризуют народные традиции в вашей стране. Расскажите то, что вы знаете, партнёру.

3. Посмотрите на русские новогодние открытки. На первой вы найдёте изображение Деда Мороза, на второй – Деда Мороза и Снегурочки.

Выполните следующие задания:

а) опишите открытки и ситуации, изображённые на них.

б) найдите в Интернете информацию о Снегурочке. Коротко расскажите о ней и её роли в новогоднем празднике.

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в) сравните русского Деда Мороза и западного Санта Клауса по следующим параметрам: внешность, одежда, атрибуты, характер и происхождение (по вашему мнению).

Таким образом, великий русский язык – один из самых богатых языков мира. Пользуясь его богатством, изучающий русский язык может выбрать точные и нужные слова для написания передачи мысли.

Использованная литература:

- 1) Монахова Т.В. «Развитие устной и письменной речи учащихся на уроках русского языка как иностранного»
- 2) Г.Хамраева., Н.Акратова «Технология подготовки будущих преподавателей русского языка и литературы к работе со студентами иноязычных групп путем развития языковых компетенций»
- 3) Г.Хамраева «Игровые технологии в преподавании русского языка»

THE ROLE OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN GLOBAL TRADE

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Annotation: This article talks about how the digital economy affects trade in different countries. The digitalization of the economy is growing rapidly, and the digital space is becoming a key area of global trade. The emergence of new formats and opportunities for international business through digitalization, the expansion of cross-border trade and invisible employment, as well as the reduction of cross-border and domestic operations in a globalized digital environment.

Key words: Digital economy, digitalization, globalization, world trade, technology, transformation, data flow, cross-border trade.

Introduction

Recently, one can find the effects of digitalization in all areas of economic activity, including global trade. World trade plays a key role in the global economy, affecting many aspects:

1. Economic Growth: Trade promotes economic growth by stimulating production, investment and innovation. Open markets allow countries to specialize in the production of goods and services in which they have a competitive advantage.
2. Job Creation: Global trade creates jobs through exports, imports and related activities in logistics, transport and trade.

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3. Increased consumer choice: Through trade, consumers have access to a wide range of goods and services at competitive prices, which increases their wealth and improves their quality of life.

4. Technological transitions: Global trade facilitates the transfer of technology and knowledge between countries, which can contribute to their technological development and modernization.

5. Geopolitical Stability: Trade can help strengthen international relations and cooperation between countries, which contributes to geopolitical stability.

6. Poverty reduction: World trade can help reduce poverty by creating opportunities for economic growth and increased incomes.

Research methodology

In the textbook “Blockchain Technologies in the Digital Economy,” written by academician S. Gulomov and others, the concept of the digital economy was defined as follows: “The digital economy (electronic) is an economy characterized by maximum satisfaction of the needs of all participants through the use of information, including personal information. This may be due to the development of information, communication and financial technologies, as well as the openness of the infrastructure, ensuring the full interaction of all economic entities in a hybrid world - the creation of goods and services, objects and entities in the process of distribution, exchange and consumption.” According to Doctor of Economic Sciences S. Mustafakulov, the digital economy is an activity that is considered as the main factor in the production of digital data, which can significantly increase the efficiency of storage, sales and delivery of a number of industries, technologies, equipment, goods and services based on the use of the results of technological analysis and processing large volumes of data.

Analyzes and results

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Today, the main question of the research is the scientific study of the patterns, trends and opportunities for the development of the digital economy in the conditions of Uzbekistan, including its use in international trade, in particular the level of penetration of information technologies in various fields. foreign economic activity. The development and prospects of our country, the success of large-scale reforms in our country are directly related to the introduction of innovations into our national economy. Therefore, it is important to improve the digital economy in foreign trade, scientific and practical study of its economic, political, social and legal framework. The research work used methods such as observation, generalization, grouping, comparison, induction and deduction.

By studying data from a survey of senior executives conducted by WEF experts in September 2015 on expected changes in the strategy and development of leading companies due to digitalization, important conclusions could be drawn. Here are some interesting results from this survey: - 88% of auto manufacturing respondents believe that by 2030, at least one of the largest automakers will generate more revenue from online sales of transportation information and services than from sales of vehicles and parts ; - 70% of representatives of companies providing various professional services believe that by 2025 digital solutions will generate more income than services provided directly by specialists;

-50% of representatives of the media and news agencies believe that by 2025, 90% of all news received by the population will be provided by computers; - 92% of representatives of the banking sector and stock market believe that by 2030, distributed ledger technology will become one of the key elements of the global financial system; - 50% of surveyed institutional investors and representatives of independent funds believe that by 2025, the majority of financial agreements and related document management will be carried out using blockchain architecture. A World Bank study entitled “Digital Dividends” shows how relevant and important

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the digital economy is to economic development. In particular, increasing Internet speed by 10 percent will increase the country's GDP. In developed countries the rate is 1.21 percent, while in developing countries it is 1.38 percent. This means that if Internet speed doubles, GDP could also increase by about 15 percent. The concept of distributed production, which is an alternative to traditional economic globalization, and its principles based on the international division of labor, natural, relative and competitive advantages that countries have, are of great interest today. The main idea of this concept is to make the process of creating new values more efficient, taking into account their interests and local conditions, bringing production closer to the buyer/consumer, participating in the development of product design and other parameters. This reduces the time spent on the production process and its cost, significantly increasing adaptability to customer requirements. For example, the entire project could rely on a network of decentralized 3D printers and IT systems connected to manufacturing company systems through soft computing. Support chains are increasingly sharing electronic messages and data transfers. Instead of a traditional support system, fast and mobile networks of many participants are formed, which interact in real time based on digital technologies. Innovative business models and technological advances are creating new opportunities to increase efficiency and reduce costs in the sale of goods and services. Consequently, the growing process of digitalization can lead to qualitative changes in all areas of domestic and foreign economic activity. Conceptual insights, statistical methods and measurements in the field of the digital economy are not yet fully developed, but sufficient data have been collected to draw preliminary conclusions in certain areas. Digitalization of the economy creates additional opportunities to increase its growth and efficiency. A report on the digital economy, commissioned by the UK government in March 2016, noted that by fully harnessing the power of digitalization, the country's gross domestic product could grow by an average of 0.4

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to 0.7 percent faster over the past decade. The basis of modern changes in the global economy and international trade is, on the one hand, the development and improvement of information technologies, filling the national economy with ICT goods and services, and on the other, the availability of mobile communications and the Internet.

The prospects for digital globalization are important for developing countries. In 2015, 70 percent of all Internet users in the world were in developing countries and countries with economies in transition, including 705 million in China, 333 million in India, 120 million in Brazil, 104 million in Russia, 87 million in Nigeria, 72 million in Mexico (for information: in the USA 242 million, in Japan - 118 million, in Germany - 72 million, in the UK - 59 million). Of the 750 million people who used the Internet for the first time between 2012 and 2015, about 90 percent were from developing countries, including 300 million from India and China. However, according to UNCTAD experts, online trade volumes in developing countries remain low. It should also be noted that countries such as China and South Korea have their own large e-commerce platforms and modern supply chain logistics systems, and the number of Internet users who buy or order goods and services online is growing every day. A new phenomenon emerging from the synthesis of digitalization and globalization, global online platforms are projected to contribute \$2.7 trillion to global GDP by 2025, create 72 million new jobs and improve economic outcomes for 540 million people.

Conclusion

The digital economy has a significant impact on global trade. Digitalization is the next stage in the development of global trade. Its impact on global trade lies in the emergence and spread of new digital technologies, the growth and strengthening of digital platforms, and the increase in the number of digital transactions. Online

platforms and e-commerce allow companies to easily reach international customers without significant investment in physical infrastructure.

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THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE ECONOMY

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ABSTRACT : This article covers the history of the origin of artificial intelligence, its development, benefits and harms in human life in military, defense, medicine and other fields.

Keywords: AI, SI, GDP, IBM, Deep Blue, IBM Watson supercomputer, Neowin.

The development of humanity, the stability of the country directly depends on the development of artificial intelligence inextricably linked. Therefore, artificial intelligence is usually associated with the capabilities of the human mind: language understanding, teaching, discussing, solving problems, some people are weak in the human factor to make certain inventions in order to further develop the fields and similar opportunities are engaged in creating the system. A simple example is computer chess players and you. Those familiar driverless vehicles, which are not new to us, are the fruit of artificial intelligence. There is a lot of rapidly developing artificial intelligence in the current technology space has an annual history. Its seeds were planted by classical thinkers defined the thinking process of people as mechanical manipulation. As an example it can be noted that to understand whether the machine can really think or no several scientific studies have been carried out. As the basis of these ideas, the 40s of the 20th century. By 1990, the first programmed digital computer working on artificial intelligence was invented is evidence that the machine is based on the essence of mathematical thinking. Of the device creation, a number of scientists to analyze the ideas in the field and a certain one in this field. It is no exaggeration to say that it inspired the publication of news. But this period the term was not named after artificial intelligence. First published in 1956 by John McCarthy held at Dartmouth College while holding his first academic position. At

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the conference, this term was presented to the public under the name "Artificial Intelligence" and conference participants McCarthy, Minsky, Shannon, Turing and others for decades have become industry leaders. They believe that smart machines will be around for a long time many investments were attracted in order to develop their projects. In 1973, in response to constant pressure from Congress and criticism from James Lighthill British government to fund research into artificial intelligence stopped, and then came a period of difficulty for this industry. This situation continued for seven years and the Japanese government artificially shut down the industry inspired the intellect to provide billions of dollars, but by the end of the 80s investors completed the financing of the project. By the first decade of the 21st century interest in artificial intelligence has begun to grow and due to investment in this field successful application of new methods to many problems in academia and industry done. For example, the Agency for Advanced Research Projects of the Ministry of Defense in the 1970 developed a number of virtual street map projects. The specialists of this project some virtual voices, such as Alice, were intelligent in 2003, long before Siri they managed to create personal assistants. These works on modern computers particularly in decision support systems and human empowerment automation and formal logic used in developed intelligent search engines became the basis for the principles. Although artificial intelligence is often used in science fiction films. Although they are described as powerful scientific robots in their works, they have their own power on a global scale occupied. The direction of artificial intelligence appeared in our country with a delay of almost 10 years and this corresponds to the first half of the 60s of the 20th century. Nowadays, artificial intelligence is rapidly developing and covers many fields. Widely used by experts in medicine, astronomy and several other fields is being used. But some say that artificial intelligence can communicate with people, imagines an ideal machine that thinks like them. Of course, this is also artificial intelligence derivative,

however, is a much more complex and broader concept. We use it daily some applications on our smartphones and computers are clear examples of artificial intelligence. For example, Google Translate, Yandex Alisa, Siri, various games and other programs we can bring. Only the scope of these applications is smaller and in a certain direction is directed. That is, from the relevant applications depending on the actions you want to perform you use. Currently, artificial intelligence is an algorithm designed to perform various actions consists of software systems and a number of tasks that can be performed by the human mind can manage. For example, an IBM computer called Deep Blue, created in the 90s we can bring. He defeated the world chess champion Garry Kasparov in history was the first computer. Another bright example of artificial intelligence is the IBM Watson supercomputer and it answers questions in a specific language based on its base. Also Siri, a mobile assistant that has become a constant companion of many people, restores photo programs such as working Prisma can be noted as one of AI's achievements. For now artificial intelligence has become widely popular in almost all of our daily lives covers all aspects. For example, bank cards to residents of Incheon in China there is no need. All processes related to calculations are performed by artificial intelligence is done by clarifying the face. Many people ask, "In which field is artificial intelligence necessary?" If the question arises, directly I can say medicine. After all, in 2020, the COVID-19 virus will not only affect China together, causing a pandemic situation with its virus that has spread all over the world, how many of our doctors are treating our patients infected with this virus themselves also caused them to fall ill with this disease and killed a large number of people. Scientists of the world artificial intelligence tools are modern to fight against this virus a powerful vaccine against this infectious disease through technologies, devices and robotics and used to find medicine. The idea is to protect our doctors from this ridiculous virus. Instead of them, a robot with artificial intelligence is introduced to look after the patients

one should be put in the hospital. They quickly went to each sick person he should measure his temperature, give necessary medicines and reach another patient.

The main reasons for replacing doctors with robots:

1. There is no risk of transmission of the Covid-19 virus. Because it is Robot With the name of the robot, he quickly looks after one patient and so together with another. He manages to get information about the patient's condition.

2. Another main reason is the lack of salary. It is state and non-state

We would not be mistaken if we say that it will be financially beneficial for organizations Robots that are the fruit of artificial intelligence are the current demand in the viral space. Contact with patients seriously ill with infectious viruses is much more difficult. In these works the demand for medical robots is high. As a result, the lives of many doctors and caused the population's health to be preserved. Artificial intelligence used to detect cancer is now COVID-1. It is also used to find the coronavirus. Software in 34 Chinese hospitals was used, and with its help, more than 32,000 cases were investigated known Our compatriot from Guzor district, Kashkadarya region in Uzbekistan created a robot working on artificial intelligence in the field of medicine. These robots disinfect intended AI is needed by humans in every field and humans benefit from these robotic system is used for the purposes. However, it cannot be done without risks. Some artificial intelligence there are aspects that pose a threat to human life Including artificial intelligence performing tasks and functions faster and at a higher level than human ability possible, and in turn, this will have a serious impact on human employment. Another aspect is artificial due to intelligence, people can have unlimited additions. This is because of anxiety may cause some problems.

In recent years, military security has emerged in the system of international relations is directly and indirectly connected to artificial intelligence in the fields of defense. The explosion of unmanned vehicles was caused by conflicts in world

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politics causing wars to become more brutal and barbaric. Now military operations become necessary, the US will manage these operations by launching drones that can do it with remote control.

Artificial intelligence has the potential to reduce human involvement in war. Firstly, artificial intelligence is necessary to participate in war and war-related operations can change the allocation of human and machine resources. Secondly, artificial intelligence affects the speed of operations, which is paradoxically decision-making reduces time. It can be said that there is no new military in the last ten years; technologies have not received more attention from experts than drones, because drones as the most visible technological tool in the modern wars of the information age is becoming popular. Also in the military successes of the United States of America the role of technological innovations is significant. The list of the most valuable companies in the world 10 years ago, by this year digital technology companies are 9 out of the Top 10 companies located.

Currently, the economic potential of nation states is based on this technology; we can observe that it is lower than the turnover and income of the companies.

According to the Accenture consulting company, 12 studies have been developed in countries that show that by 2035, artificial intelligence will be able to double the global economic growth rate. This increase is threefold, characterized by the following aspects.

Firstly, it is up to 40% of labor productivity due to innovative technologies leading to strong growth and more effective time management related to the workforce allows.

Second, AI creates a new virtual workforce: it's called "intelligent automation" and will have the functions of problem solving and self-management.

Thirdly, the economy affects various sectors and new income will also benefit from the spread of innovations that create resources.

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According to McKinsey Global Institute observations, artificial intelligence by 2030 production of additional economic output in the amount of approximately 13 trillion US dollars it is possible to increase the global GDP, i.e. gross domestic product, by approximately 1.2% annually is carried out at the expense of

In conclusion, it can be said that starting with the history of artificial intelligence, it was written about its benefits and harms in the fields. It is known to everyone that every lease is different there are advantages and disadvantages. Never if we only talk about the damage we cannot grow. If we make good use of its useful aspects, we will be more prosperous in the development of our time adds. But along with these benefits are unemployment, cybercrime, and military risks we need to be careful. It is not surprising that some of these problems will be completely solved in the future.

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THE ROLE OF DIGITIZATION IN THE ECONOMY

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ABSTRACT: *The article discusses the importance of the digital economy, which is a modern requirement, and the benefits of its implementation in our country.*

KEYWORDS: *digital technology, digital economy, engineering, economics.*

The increase in the share of innovative activity has led to the fact that innovations are the same such as minerals, production capacity and intellectual capacity the country's wealth began to be counted. Our country and each of its citizens effective use of innovative and scientific and technical potential in the interests of formation of a multi-sectoral innovation policy in our country and its implementation to increase - there is no possibility without creating legal bases. The head of our state said, "... our country is an international information in 2019 according to the index of development of communication technologies although it has risen to the top, it is still far behind. Most ministries and agencies, It is also true that companies are far from digital technologies. Of course, Building a digital economy requires infrastructure, a lot of money and labor we know very well that it requires resources. However, no matter how difficult it is If we don't start work today, when will we start?! Tomorrow will be too late. To this end, active transition to the digital economy is one of our most important tasks in the next 5 year will be. Digital technologies not only improve the quality of products and services, but also reduces costs. At the same time, I am very worried and they are also effective in eliminating the most serious evil that bothers us - corruption is a tool. We all need to understand this deeply. State and community management, widely introducing digital technologies in the social sphere and increasing productivity, one in other words, people's lives can be dramatically improved." President

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Shavkat Mirziyoyev in his appeals to the Oliy Majlis 202 declared the year as the "Year of Development of Science, Enlightenment and Digital Economy" It can be noted with satisfaction, pride and pride that this is an appeal not only in the guide and guide for 2020, but perhaps Uzbekistan is close It is fundamental as a program that determines the path of development in the medium term can be considered as an important historical document. In general, any Science, including economics, and society is more important than mathematical achievements if you don't use it, you can't get high.

Relevance of the article

According to the results of various studies, the world of the digital economy its weight in the economy ranges from 4.5 to 15.5 percent. Almost of the added value created in the world information and communication technology sector 40% and 75% of patents related to blockchain technologies are American. It corresponds to the contribution of the United States and the People's Republic of China. The President of our country Sh.M. Mirziyoyev's information on February 13, 202 the statistician gave at the event dedicated to the development of technology according to the data of the digital economy in the United States in the gross domestic product share is 10.9 percent, 10 percent in China, 5.5 percent in India. This is in Uzbekistan the indicator does not exceed 2 percent. How much the importance and impact of digitization is increasing to evaluate several major technology companies of the last decade and it is enough to see the share of capital of digital platforms in the world market. In our country, the legal system is being developed for the development of the digital economy studying propaganda;

- The place of the digital economy in the development of the countries of the world study;
- Analysis of reforms in our country in numbers;
- Expressing conclusions and suggestions.

However, in the context of the global economic crisis, enterprises and scientific groups the task of improving the efficiency of the use of allocated funds is in the first place stands In this regard, we come across the concept of economic efficiency. For these purposes,

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every year in the countries of the European Union, Europe is innovative indicators (YIK) are published. Also in 2007, one of the European Union technical efficiency based on the method of analyzing the working environment for a number of countries indicators were calculated. People of the world say that digital technologies depend on the economy 50 will dramatically change more than 100% of industries. This view is informative technologies and digital platforms dramatically change business models and their efficiency to eliminate intermediaries and optimize processes based. According to World Bank calculations, 10 of fast internet users percent increase can increase the annual GDP from 0.4 percent to 1.4 percent it is. Also, the share of the digital economy in the country's GDP is approx 20 percent growth (in developed countries this indicator is around 7 percent) is it is considered as an indicator that determines its importance. Boston Consulting in 2010. The Group's digitization rate is 2.3 for a group of 20 countries trillion dollars (4.1 percent of GDP). If this trend continues, 10-15 after the year, the share of such an economy in the world GDP will approach 30-40 percent. "Uzbektelecom" is an example of the results of the reforms carried out in our country. We can take the activity of a joint stock company. Administrative in our country simplifying the process of transition, improving the quality of life of the population, investment and including e-government aimed at improving the business environment in terms of modernization and development of the state service delivery system "Uzbekista Digital economy, e-government and information to public administration of the Republic PF-5598 "On additional measures for the introduction of systems Farmoni is a clear example of this.

Instead of conclusions and suggestions, it is worth saying that humanity is for development. It is clear only if it is carried out with the aim of making life easier the plan can be used. In the current period and near future of human development in terms of the quality of economic sectors, social sphere and state management system development is directly related to the widespread introduction of digital technologies is going. The prospect of our country's development is the development of the digital economy and relies on the level of

coverage of digital technologies. To achieve the following basic conditions and priorities for the development of the digital economy it is appropriate to list the directions. It is no exaggeration to say that the literacy of the population is a step forward in this regard. It is the same in our country: digital technology for public literacy at leisure. At the same time, the process of training specialists in this field is being strengthened. Leading specialists are currently lacking in digitization is also hindering; Number of activities of total schools in the field of secondary education. If we are not connected to technology, it is difficult to see the future towards a long digital life and hard work; an enterprise that is currently operating increasing the level of knowledge of employees, suitable for modern technical activities incentives that create a favorable opportunity for special tests or monthly salary. If we don't use it, we will separate the techniques in this field from the breath of the past we can't; Although the above suggestions may seem simple to you, they are actually ours that you and we can be the prelude to our foundation for future development we know well.

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“ Сутканинг вақтига қараб пойтахтимиз ҳудудида
содир этилаётган ЙТҲларининг таҳлили”

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Аннотация:

Республикамизда, айниқса пойтахтда транспорт воситалари оқимининг кескин ошиб бориши, содир этилаётган йўл-транспорт ҳодисаларининг кунинг қайси вақти бўлишидан қатъий назар кескин равишда йўл-транспорт ҳодисаларининг ошиб кетиши натижасида ҳайдовчилар ва йўловчиларнинг ҳалок бўлган ҳамда жароҳат олганлар сони ўсиши ҳамда уларнинг олдини олиш, камайтириш чора-тадбирлари ҳақида.

Abstract:

On the increase in the flow of vehicles in our country, especially in the city of Tashkent, the increase in the number of deaths and injuries of drivers and passengers as a result of a sharp increase in traffic accidents, regardless of the time of day, and measures to prevent and reduce them.

Калит сўзлар: ҳаракатни нотўғри ташкил этиш, бахтсиз ҳодиса, сутка, кун, тун, вақт, йўлларнинг ҳолати, мавжуд инфратузилма, авария ўчоқлари.

Key words: improper Organization of movement, accident, Day, Night, Time, condition of roads, existing insfratuzilma, accident foci.

Ўзбекистоннинг доимий аҳолиси 2024 йилнинг 01 январь ҳолатига кўра 36 млн. 799 минг 800 кишини ташкил этиб, шу билан бирга жисмоний шахсларга тегишли автомобиллар сони 4 млн. 20 мингни ташкил этиб, бир йил

давомида кшрсаткич салкам 400 мингтага кўпайган. Аҳолига тегишли жами автотранспорт воситаларидан 93 % енгил автомобиллар ташкил этади. Сўнгги вақтларда юртимизда транспорт воситалари ошиши, транспорт воситалари оқимининг кескин кўпайиши, сутканинг ҳоҳлаган вақтида, куннинг қайси вақти бўлишидан қатъий назар кескин равишда ЙТХларининг ошиб кетиши натижасида ҳайдовчилар ва йўловчиларнинг ҳалок бўлган ва тан жароҳати олганлар сони ортиб бормоқда.

Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти Ш.М.Мирзиёев ташшабуслари билан диёримизда, айниқса Пойтахтимиз йўлларида кунинг қайси вақти бўлишидан қатъий назар йўл-транспорт ҳодисаларининг олдини олишга катта эътибор қаратилмоқда.

Пойтахтимиз Тошкентда 2023 йилнинг 12 ойида ўлим билан боғлиқ ЙТХни сутка давомида кўриб чиқадиган бўлсак, қуйидагиларни кўришимиз мумкин:

Ўлим билан боғлиқ ЙТХнинг ВАҚТИ бўйича:

- соат 06:00 дан – 12:00 гача - 22 та
- соат 12:00 дан – 18:00 гача - 41 та
- соат 18:00 дан – 24:00 гача - 59 та
- соат 24:00 дан – 06:00 гача – 26 та

Ўлим билан боғлиқ ЙТХ куннинг ЁРУҒ ВА ҚОРОНҒИ вақтлари бўйича:

- куннинг ёруғ вақтида – 63 нафар;
- куннинг қоронғи вақтида – 85 нафар одам ҳалок бўлган.

Ўлим билан боғлиқ ЙТХда ҳалок бўлган ШАХСЛАР бўйича:

- ҳайдовчи - 34 нафар;
- йўловчи - 28 нафар;
- пиёдалар - 86 нафар;

Айниқса, сутканинг соат 18.00 дан 24.00 га қадар ЙТХлар сони ўсганлиги ва бунда жароҳат олганлар ва вафот этганлар сони ошганлигини шунингдек кундузи соат 12.00 дан 18.00 га қадар ҳам ушбу кўрсаткич ўсганлигини кузатишимиз мумкин.

Диаграмма №1

Ушбу кўрсаткични ҳафта мобайнида кўрмоқчи бўлсак, ЙТХ ҳафтанинг сешанба ва шанба кунларида ўсганлигини кўрамиз. Масалан, сешанба куни жами ЙТХ сони ўтган 2023 йилнинг 12 ойида 221 тани /2022 йилнинг шу даврида 184 тани/ , ҳалок бўлганлар 27/26 нафарни, жароҳат олганлар 238/204 нафарни ташкил этган бўлса, ҳафтанинг шанба куни бу кўрсаткичлар жами

содир этилган ЙТХлар сони 246/217 тани, ҳалок бўлганлар 28/24 ва жароҳат олганлар 276/248 нафарни ташкил этган.

Айнан инсон омили билан боғлиқ бўлган йўл транспорт ҳодисаларининг асосий сабаби, ҳайдовчиларнинг оралик масофани сақламаганликлари, белгиланган тезликка риоя этмаслиги, ҳайдовчининг тажрибасизлиги ҳамда пиёдаларга йўл бермаслик, светофор ва йўл белгиларига риоя қилмаслик каби ҳолатлар билан бирга йўлда хушёрликни йўқотиши ва ўзига бўлган ишончни ошиб кетишлиги, йўлларда ҳам “огоҳлик - давр талаби” деган тушунчага амал қилмасликлари, сутканинг айниқса ёруғ вақтида бунга бефарқлиги бўлмоқда.

Диаграмма № 2

Хулоса қилиб айтганда, пойтахтимизда йўл-транспорт ҳодисаларининг ошиб кетиши натижасида ҳайдовчи ва йўловчиларнинг ҳалок бўлган ҳамда

жароҳат олганлар сони ўсиши ва уларни олдини олиш, камайтириш ҳамда самарадорлиги :

-Ҳайдовчилар томонидан йўл ҳаракати қондасини бузилишини айнан ЙТҲ куннинг ёруғ ва қоронғи пайтларида энг кўп содир бўлаётган жойларни аниқлаш ҳамда керакли чора-тадбирлар ишлаб чиқиш;

-Йўл-транспорт ҳодисаларининг содир бўлган жойларда йўл ҳаракати хавфсизлиги даражасини ошириш учун ноқулай омилларни бартараф этишга қаратилган керакли чора тадбирларни режалаштириш;

-Режалаштирилган тадбирларнинг самарадорлигини ва уларни амалга ошириш натижасида бахтсиз ҳодисалар сонининг тахминий камайишини ҳисобга олган ҳолда тадбирларни ўтказиш харажатларини баҳолаш;

-Ҳайдовчилар томонидан транспорт воситаларининг бошқаришда куннинг ёруғ ва қоронғи вақтларига ЙТҲлари содир этилгандан сўнг бошқарув орқали тезкор ва тизимли ҳаракатини таъминлашдир.

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**PIRIMQUL QODIROV YON DAFTARIDAN O'RIN OLGAN
BITIKLARDA IJODKOR DUNYOQARASHINING AKS ETTIRILISHI**

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Pirimqul Qodirovning estetik qarashlari aks etgan "Yon daftari"dan o'rin olgan falsafiy, adabiy mushohadalar mazmun jihatidan muhokama etilgan. Tahlil jarayonida yozuvchi dunyoqarashining o'ziga xos qirralari ochib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: hissiy idrok, o'zbek adabiyoti, badia, ilmiy va publististik maqola, ma'naviy kamolot, estetik konsepsiya

**ОТРАЖЕНИЕ ТВОРЧЕСКОЙ МИРОВОЗГРАЖДЕНИЯ В НАДПИСЯХ
ИЗ БЛОКНОТА ПИРИМКУЛЯ КАДИРОВА**

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Аннотация: В данной статье содержательно рассматриваются философско-литературные наблюдения из «Блокнот», отражающие эстетические взгляды Пиримкуля Кадырова. В процессе анализа раскрываются уникальные стороны мировоззрения писателя.

Ключевые слова: эмоциональное восприятие, узбекская литература, искусство, научно-публицистическая статья, духовная зрелость, эстетическая концепция.

**THE REFLECTION OF THE CREATIVE WORLD VIEW IN THE
INSCRIPTIONS FROM THE SIDE NOTEBOOK OF PIRIMQUL
KADIROV**

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Abstract: In this article, the philosophical and literary observations from the "Yon Daftari", which reflect the aesthetic views of Pirimkul Kadyrov, are discussed in terms of content. In the process of analysis, the unique aspects of the worldview of the writer are revealed.

Key words: emotional perception, Uzbek literature, art, scientific and journalistic article, spiritual maturity, aesthetic concept

Kirish

Ijod jarayonida iste'dod tarozisi faqat badiiy asar yozish yoki qalb tug'yonida kechayotgan ilhom po'rtanalarini qog'ozga tushirish mahorati bilangina emas, badiiy asarlar haqida falsafiy mushohada qilmoq, tandqid qila bilmoq, kuzata bilmoq mas'uliyati va qobiliyati bilan ham o'lchanadi. Ijodkorlarning adabiy qarashlarini o'rganish eng avvalo uning adabiy-estetik konsepsiyani aniqlash hamda hissiy va aqliy idrok chegaralarini kuzatish maqsadida, hamda adabiyot ixlosmandlari uchun dasturulamal bo'la olishi mumkinligi jihatidan ham ahamiyatlidir.

Asosiy qism

O‘zbek adabiyoti tarixida ham adabiyotshunoslar doimiy ravishda murojaat qiladigan, qolipga solingan, tayyor adabiyot nazariyasidan farq qiladigan, o‘z navbatida to‘ldiradigan fikr-mulohazalar borligi tabiiy hol. Abdulla Qodiriyning «Yozuvchining o‘z ishi to‘g‘risida», «Kulgu haqida» kabi qator maqolalari, Abdulla Qahhorning «Yoshlar bilan suhbat»i, Oybek yoki G‘afur G‘ulomning, Odil Yoqubovning, Shukur Xolmirzayev yoki O‘tkir Hoshimovning, adabiy qarashlari Erkin Vohidovning “Shoiru she’ru shuur”, Abdulla Oripovning “Ehtiyoj farzandi” kabi nomli kitoblarida jamlangan mulohazalari-yu kuzatishlari adabiyot vakillari uchun ana shunday qimmatli manbaa bo‘lib kelmoqda. Ana shunday manbaalar sirasiga Pirmqul Qodirovning adabiy-estetik qarashlari jamlangan til haqida yozilgan “Xalq tili va realistik proza”, “Til va El” badiolari, “Amir Temur siymosi” tarixiy badiasini, “Qalb ko‘zlari” badiasi hamda ilmiy va publististik maqolalarini kiritsak bo‘ladi.

Natijalar va muhokamalar

Barcha ilmiy tadqiqotlar, katta –katta ilmiy va adabiy mulohazalar kichik adabiy fikrlar va maqolalardan boshlanadi. Pirmqul Qodirovning shogirdi, jurnalist va adabiyotshunos **To‘lqin Eshbekning** “Pirmqul Qodirov saboqlari” deb nomlangan maqolasida ijodkorning “Yon daftari”dan olingan bir qancha satrlari keltiriladi. Pirmqul Qodirov ko‘p qirrali yozuvchi. U bir vaqtning o‘zida tarixchi, tilshunos, siyosatchi-diplomat hisoblanadi. Shu bilan bir qatorda o‘z vatanining sodiq vatanparvar fuqarosi hamdir. Shu boisdan uning “Yon daftari”dan o‘rin olgan satrlarni mazmun jihatidan shartli ravishda quyidagicha guruhlash mumkin:

1. Adabiyotga oid fikrlar;
2. Hayot haqidagi falsafalar;
3. Amir Temur va temuriylar saltanati haqidagi mushohadalar;
4. Vatanparvarlik va ma’naviy kamolot borasidagi mushohadalar

Adib **adabiyotga oid fikrlarining** birida iste'dodni bahorga qiyoslaydi: *“Adabiy iste'dodda bahordagiga o'xshash bir kuch bo'ladi. U tasvirlagan hamma narsa ichki bir latofatga to'lib turadi. Adabiy iste'dod ham bahor kabi daraxtlarning so'ligan yoki so'limaganini farqlab beradi. Agar iste'dod ham so'ligan daraxt kabi bo'lsa, u gullamaydi. Yoki aksincha yangi ekilgan nihol kabi bo'lsa, u hali gulga kirmaydi. Bahor ham “o'z qudrati bilan tirik daraxtni yashnatib, o'ligini butun xunukligicha fosh qilib” ko'rsatganidek, ma'naviyat olamida bahor kabi oqni oqqa, qorani qoraga ajratadi deya o'ziga xos muqoyasa qiladi.*¹ Darhaqiqat, iste'dodni bahorga qiyoslash ijodkorning estetikasiga go'zallik bahosini bergan. Adibning ijod laboratoriyasida faqatgina adabiy mulohazalar emas, hayot, umr mazmuni haqida falsafiy mushohadalariga ham duch kelamiz: u inson hayot yo'li haqida fikr yuritar ekan, insondan faqat ezgu ishlar qolishi kerakligini va undan qolgan yaxshiliklar go'yoki *gilamdagi guldek yoki bog'dagi chinordek* bo'lib qolishi lozimligini ta'kidlaydi.

Yozuvchi **hayot va umr mazmuni**, shukronalik haqida fikr yuritar ekan, inson hayotidan ortiqcha nolishi kerak emasligini aytib o'tish baobarida, eng katta *boylik bo'lmish vaqtni hali yozilmagan oppoq qog'ozga va to'qilmagan gilam guliga va hech narsa ekilmagan dalalarga qiyos etadi. Bekor o'tgan vaqt – oq kelib-oq ketgan varaq, ekinsiz tashlab qo'yilgan dala. Mabodo, oq varaqqa yomon narsa yozib qo'ysak, o'chirganimiz bilan izi qoladi. Mabodo, bizga in'om etilgan dala qarovsiz qolsa, uni yovvoyi o'tlar, sassiq alaflar bosib ketadi...*² Yozuvchining ushbu qiyosidan anglashiladiki, umr insonga berilgan tortiqdir. Uni go'zal bog'ga aylantirish ham mumkin, yovvoyi o'tlar bosgan qarovsiz dalaga aylantirish ham mumkin.

¹ “PIRIMQUL QODIROV SABOQLARI.” To'lqin EShBEK, <https://kh-davron.uz/>,25.10.2021

² “PIRIMQUL QODIROV SABOQLARI.” To'lqin EShBEK, <https://kh-davron.uz/>,25.10.2021

Tarixiy romanlar ustasi bo'lgan adib “Yon daftari” dan joy olgan **Amir Temur va temuriylar** haqidagi qimmatli fikrlarini “Amir Temur siymosi”, “Ona lochin vidosi”, Bobur va Boburiylar haqidagi mushohadalarini “Yulduzli tunlar” hamda “Avlodlar dovoni” asarlarida o'z aksini topib keng quloch yoyadi. Yozuvchi Amir Temur shaxsi haqida fikr yuritib, u haqida turli to'qib bichilgan gaplarga, yolg'on ma'lumotlarga yo'l qo'ymaslik kerakligini ta'kidlaydi. Shuningdek, uning ismiga qo'shib aytiladigan Tarag'ay Bahodir nisbasiga ham munosabat bildiradi. Uning **To'rg'ay** deb deb noto'g'ri atab kelinishini qoralab aslida bu nisbat **Tarag'ay**- nurday taralsin, ko'paysin ma'nosini berishini izohlaydi.³ Ushbu fikrlar adib yon daftariga qoralama tarzida yozib qo'yilgan qoralama tarzidagi satrlar bo'lsa-da, ijodkor estetik qarashlarining tarixiylik qirralariga ishora qilib turibdi.

Ma'naviy ehtiyoj va Vatanparvarlik haqida adibning estetik qarashlari ham ushbu yon daftardan o'rin olgan va Vatan haqidagi falsafiy fikrlari Bobur obrazining iztiroblarini yaqqol muqoyasa qilingandek go'yo. Aynan shu roman yozilayotgan paytda ijodkorning qalbidan o'tgan kechinmalari, hissiy idrokning bu kabi purma'no nuri mana shunday takrorlanmas hikmatlarning yuzaga chiqishiga sabab bo'lgandir. Ijodkorning estetik konsepsiyaasini ko'zdan kechirar ekanmiz, uning ma'naviyatga, ma'rifatga e'tibori o'zgacha ekanligini sezamiz. Negaki, fikrlarida ma'naviyat va ruh kamoloti haqida qimmatli fikrlarning uchrab turishi, hamda **“Ma'naviyat, modernizm va absurd”**⁴ maqolasida adabiyotning inson ma'naviyati uchun xizmat qilmog'i kerakligi haqidagi mushohadalar fikrimizning isbotidir.

Adib yon daftaridan joy olgan ushbu mulohazalar keyichalik uning **“Adabiy o'ylar”** va **“Qalb ko'zlari”** badialaridan joy oladi. **“Qalb ko'zlari”** kitobining

³ PIRIMQUL QODIROV SABOQLARI. To'lqin EShBEK, <https://kh-davron.uz/>,25.10.2021

⁴ Qarang:P.Qodirov.Ma'naviyat, modernizm va absurd.- O'zbekiston adabiyoti va san'ati 2004-yil 26-mart,

“Nur to’la ummon”, “Falsafiy lavhalar” kabi qismlaridan ana shu yon daftardan joy olgan o’ylarning batafsil mushohadasi o’rin olgan.⁵

Xulosa

Xulosa qilib aytganda, xalqimiz suygan adib Pirimqul Qodirov ijodi nihoyatda serqirra va rang-barang hisoblanadi. Uning ijod bulog’idan tomgan bir tomchi bo’lgan ushbu mulohazalar adibning ilhom pallasida gullagan boychechak kabidir. Ijodkorning adabiy qarashlar, estetik konsepsiyalari filologiya sohasida hali o’rganilishi talab etilayotgan mavzudir, desak adashmaymiz.

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⁵ Pirimqul Qodirov “Qalb ko’zlari” Toshkent, Ma’naviyat nashriyoti 2001-yil

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Mahalla huquq tartibot maskanlari faoliyati.

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Annotatsiya: O'zbekiston Respublikasi Ichki Ishlar Vazirligi tizimidagi eng quyida tuzilma hisoblanagan Mahalla huquq tartibot maskani tushunchasi, maqsadi uning faoliyatining asosiy yo'nalishlari, tuzilishi va tarkibiy tuzilmasi haqida, tayanch punkti va mahalla huquq tartibot maskanining asosiy farqli jihatlari muhokama qilinadi.

Аннотация: Понятие «Соседский центр правопорядка», который считается низшей структурой в системе МВД Республики Узбекистан, основные направления его деятельности, его структура и структурная структура, основные отличия между Обсуждается основная тема и районный центр правопорядка.

Annotation: The concept of the Neighborhood Law and Order Center, which is considered the lowest structure in the system of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the main directions of its activity, its structure and structural structure, the main differences between the main point and the neighborhood law and order center are discussed.

Kalit so'zlar: Tayanch punkti, Mahalla huquq tartibot maskani, inson qadri, modernizatsiya, Smart mahalla, xonadonbay, profilaktika katta inspektori, hamkorlik, haql manfaatlari.

Ключевые слова: Базовая точка, Соседство, место правопорядка, человеческая ценность, модернизация, Умное соседство, экономка, старший инспектор по профилактике, сотрудничество, интересы человека.

Key words: Base point, Neighborhood, place of law and order, human value, modernization, Smart neighborhood, housekeeper, prevention senior inspector,

cooperation, human interests.

Dunyoda inson qadrini oshirish, uning hayot tarzini yuksaltirish, ijtimoiy hayotda o'z o'rnini topish va sog'lom turmush tarzini olib borish bo'yicha ko'plab davlatlar va xalqaro tashkilotlar tomonidan ishlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Inson hayotiga bugungi kunda salbiy jihatdan tasir ko'rsatuvchi ko'plab sabablar mavjud. Bu kabi salbiy illatlarga ko'plab misollar keltirish mumkun. Ijtimoiy hayotda ishsizlik, surunkali ichkilikbozlik va giyohvandlik kabi salbiy illatlar insonni tubsiz jarlikka boshlaydi.

Bu borada yurtimizda huquqbuzarliklarni oldinibarvaq oldini olish uchun ichki ishlar tizimida Mahalla huquq tartibot maskani tashkil etildi. Bizni avvalambor tayanch punkti nima ekanligini bilib olishimiz lozim.

Tayanch punktlari tuman (shahar) ichki ishlar boshqarmalari (bo'limlari)ning asosiy quyi bo'g'ini hisoblanib, ular ichki ishlar organlarining jamoatchilik bilan hamkorligini ta'minlash hamda qishloqlar, ovullar va mahallalarda jamoat tartibi, fuqarolar xavfsizligi, huquqbuzarliklar profilaktikasi hamda jinoyatchilikka qarshi kurashishni bevosita ta'minlash maqsadida tashkil etiladi. Oddiy qilib aytadigan bo'lsak tayanch punktlari har bir mahallada xavfsizlikni ta'minlovchi tuzilmadir.

Tayanch punktlari o'z faoliyatini profilaktika katta inspektorlari va profilaktika inspektorlari tarkibida amalga oshiradilar Tayanch punktlari faoliyatini tashkil etish uchun ichki ishlar organlarining boshqa bo'linmalari ham jalb etilishi mumkin.

Barcha sohalarda islohotlar bo'lgani kabi Ichki ishlar organlarida ham bir qator islohotlar amalga oshirildi 2021-yil 26-mart kuni "Jamoat xavfsizligini ta'minlash va jinoyatchilikka qarshi kurashish sohasida ichki ishlar organlari faoliyatini sifat jihatidan yangi bosqichga ko'tarish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida" PF-6196-son Prezident farmoni qabul qilindi. Ushbu farmon asosida bir qator ishlar

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amalga oshirildi va ichki ishlar organlari quyi tizimini modernizatsiya qilish yuzasidan bir qator kompleks chora tadbirlar belgilab olindi.

Tizimga raqamli texnologiyalarni qo‘llash va aholiga yana-da qulaylik yaratish maqsadida, profilaktika inspektorlariga masofadan turib murojaat qilish va uni ko‘rib chiqish jarayonini kuzatib borish, aholi bilan o‘zaro tezkor muloqotni yo‘lga qo‘yish imkonini beruvchi “Smart mahalla” dasturi ishlab chiqilmoqda.

Mazkur Farmonda ichki ishlar organlarining tayanch punktlari negizida mahalla huquq-tartibot maskanlari tashkil etilishi belgilandi. Ta’kidlash joizki, mahalla huquq-tartibot maskani hududdagi jamoat xavfsizligini ta’minlash, huquqbuzarliklarning oldini olish va jinoyatchilikka qarshi kurashishning asosiy quyi bo‘g‘ini hisoblanadi. Maskan negizida hududdagi ichki ishlar organlarining tegishli sohaviy xizmatlari hamda Milliy gvardiya va boshqa davlat organlarining muvofiqlashtirilgan faoliyati tashkil etiladi. Shuningdek, maskan tomonidan jamoat xavfsizligini ta’minlash, huquqbuzarliklarning oldini olish va jinoyatchilikka qarshi kurashish ishlarini tizimli tashkil etish va muvofiqlashtirish vazifasi profilaktika inspektoriga yuklandi. Tizimga raqamli texnologiyalarni qo‘llash va aholiga yana-da qulaylik yaratish maqsadida, profilaktika inspektorlariga masofadan turib murojaat qilish va uni ko‘rib chiqish jarayonini kuzatib borish, aholi bilan o‘zaro tezkor muloqotni yo‘lga qo‘yish imkonini beruvchi “Smart mahalla” dasturi ishlab chiqilmoqda. Maskanlarning asosiy vazifalari qilib quyidagilar belgilangan

- ✓ mahallada (qishloqda) jamoat tartibini saqlash, huquqbuzarliklar profilaktikasi va jinoyatchilikka qarshi kurashishni bevosita amalga oshirish;
- ✓ fuqarolarning xavfsizligi va osoyishtaligini ta’minlash borasida ichki ishlar organlari, boshqa davlat organlari va jamoat tuzilmalarining mahallalar kesimida birgalikda ishlashini tashkil etish;
- ✓ aholi muammolarini hal etish, shuningdek, huquqbuzarlikdan jabrlangan, g‘ayriijtimoiy xulq-atvorga ega, huquqbuzarlik sodir etgan shaxslarni ijtimoiy

moslashtirish ishlarini tashkil etish;

- ✓ mahallaning (qishloqning) kirish-chiqish joylarida va hududdagi boshqa obyektlarda o'rnatilgan videokuzatuv moslamalaridan foydalangan holda, yagona markazlashgan elektron kuzatish va monitoringni amalga oshirish orqali huquqbuzarliklarni barvaqt oldini olish, aniqlash va fosh etish.

Maskanlar binolariga qo'yiladigan talablar va ularda faoliyatni olib borish tartibi O'zbekiston Respublikasi ichki ishlar vaziri tomonidan belgilanadi.

Maskanlar o'z faoliyatini quyidagicha tarkibda amalga oshiradilar

- profilaktika katta inspektori, profilaktika inspektori, profilaktika inspektorining jamoat tartibini saqlash bo'yicha yordamchisi (har kunlik asosida);
- hududda xizmat qilish uchun birlashtirilgan tuman (shahar) ichki ishlar organining xotin-qizlar masalalari bo'yicha inspektori, probatsiya bo'linmasi inspektori, tezkor vakil, patrul-post xizmati xodimlari;
- hududda jamoat tartibini saqlash va huquqbuzarliklar profilaktikasiga ko'maklashish uchun yuborilgan Milliy gvardiya bo'linmasi, boshqa vakolatli davlat organlarining xodimlari va jamoat tuzilmalarining vakillari tarkibida amalga oshiradi.

Profilaktika katta inspektori Maskanning bevosita rahbari hisoblanadi va uning zimmasiga mahallada (qishloqda) jamoat tartibini saqlash va huquqbuzarliklar profilaktikasi bo'yicha kunlik ishni samarali tashkil etish mas'uliyati yuklanadi.

Profilaktika (katta) inspektori quyidagilarga majbur;

Maskan faoliyatiga yuklatilgan vazifalarning lozim darajada bajarilishi uchun shaxsan javobgar bo'ladi;

Maskanda faoliyat ko'rsatadigan xodimlarga yuklatilgan vazifalarning bajarilishini nazorat qiladi, hududda patrul yo'nalishlarini belgilaydi va patrullik xizmatini tashkil etadi;

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hududda jamoat tartibini saqlash va huquqbuzarliklar profilaktikasiga ko‘maklashish uchun yuborilgan Milliy gvardiya bo‘linmasi, boshqa vakolatli davlat organlarining xodimlari va jamoat tuzilmalari vakillarining faoliyatini muvofiqlashtiradi;

Maskanning ish rejalarini tasdiqlaydi;

vazifalarini sidqidildan bajarib kelayotgan profilaktika inspektorining jamoat tartibini saqlash bo‘yicha yordamchisiga ichki ishlar organlarida xizmatga belgilangan tartibda qabul qilish uchun tavsiyaviy taqdimnoma kiritadi;

Maskanda samarali faoliyat ko‘rsatadigan xodimlarni rag‘batlantirish to‘g‘risida hududiy ichki ishlar organi rahbariga to‘g‘ridan-to‘g‘ri taklif kiritadi.

Profilaktika katta inspektori yo‘qligida uning vakolatlari profilaktika inspektori tomonidan amalga oshiriladi.

Ish yuritish va maxfiylik tartiboti bo‘yicha tadbirlar Maskan tomonidan o‘rnatilgan tartibda amalga oshiriladi.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR RO‘YXATI

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining “Jamoat xavfsizligini ta’minlash va jinoyatchilikka qarshi kurashish sohasida ichki ishlar organlari faoliyatini sifat jihatidan yangi bosqichga ko‘tarish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida” 2021-yil 26-mart kunidagi PF-6196-son Prezident farmoni.
2. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining «O‘zbekiston Respublikasi jamoat xavfsizligi konsepsiyasini tasdiqlash va uni amalga oshirish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida» 2021 yil 29 noyabrdagi PF-27-son Farmoni
3. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining «Ichki ishlar organlarining jamoat xavfsizligini ta’minlash va jinoyatchilikka qarshi kurashish sohasidagi faoliyatini yanada takomillashtirish bo‘yicha

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qo‘shimcha tashkiliy chora-tadbirlar to‘g‘risida» 2021 yil 2 apreldagi PQ-5050-son qarori

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**Profilaktika inspektorining terrorizm va
ekstremizm bilan bog‘liq jinoyatlar profilaktikasi
faoliyati**

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O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI ICHKI ISHLAR VAZIRLIGI AKADEMIYASI

HUQUQBUZARLIKLAR PROFILAKTIKASI FAOLIYATI KAFEDRASI

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Annotatsiya: mazkur maqolada profilaktika inspektorining terrorizm va ekstremizm bilan bog‘liq jinoyatlar profilaktikasini samarali amalga oshirishda va ushbu faoliyatni tashkil etilishiga to‘sqinlik qilayotgan muammolarni aniqlash va ularni bartaraf qilishga, ushbu faoliyatni yanada takomillashtirishga xizmat qiluvchi taklif va tavsiyalar ishlab chiqish hisoblanadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: profilaktika inspektorining terrorizm va ekstremizm bilan bog‘liq jinoyatlar profilaktikasi faoliyati, terrorizm, ekstremizm, terrorchi, terrorchilik tashkiloti, terrorchilik guruhi, xalqaro terrorizm, diniy ekstremizm, diniy fundamentalizm, huquqbuzarliklar profilaktikasi, huquqbuzarliklar profilaktikasi ishi, huquqbuzarliklar profilaktikasini amalga oshiruvchi organ va muassasalar.

Annotation: in this article, it is considered to be the development of proposals and recommendations that serve to identify and eliminate the problems that prevent the prevention of crimes related to terrorism and extremism, and the organization of this activity, and to further improve this activity.

Key words: activities of the prevention inspector to prevent crimes related to terrorism and extremism, terrorism, extremism, terrorist, terrorist organization, terrorist group, international terrorism, religious extremism, religious fundamentalism, crime prevention, crime prevention work, crime prevention

practitioner bodies and institutions.

Bugungi kunda O‘zbekiston Respublikasida amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlarning barchasi yurtboshimiz Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev tomondan konseptual g‘oya sifatida mustahkamlangan “Inson qadri uchun” degan tamoyil asosida amalga oshirilmoqda. Mamlakatimizda mustaqillik yillarida amalga oshirilgan keng ko‘lamli islohotlarning natijasi sifatida milliy davlatchilik va suverinitetni mustahkamlash, xavfsizlik va huquq – tartibotni, davlatimiz chegaralari daxlsizligini, jamiyatda qonun ustuvorligini, inson huquq va erkinliklari uchun muhim poydevor bo‘ldi, xalqimizning munosib hayot kechirishi, fuqarolarimizning bunyodkorlik salohiyatini ro‘yobga chiqarish uchun zarur shart – sharoitlar yaratdi.

Dunyoda inson qadrini oshirish, uning hayot tarzini yuksaltirish, ijtimoiy hayotda o‘z o‘rnini topish va sog‘lom turmush tarzini olib borish bo‘yicha ko‘plab davlatlar va xalqaro tashkilotlar tomonidan ishlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Inson hayotiga bugungi kunda salbiy jihatdan tasir ko‘rsatuvchi ko‘plab sabablar mavjud. Bu kabi salbiy illatlarga ko‘plab misollar keltirish mumkun. Ijtimoiy hayotda ishsizlik, surunkali ichkilikbozlik va giyohvandlik kabi salbiy illatlar insonni tubsiz jarlikka boshlaydi.

Olib borilayotgan islohotlar samarasini yanada oshirish, davlat va jamiyatning har tomonlama va jadal rivojlanishi uchun shart – sharoitlar yaratish, mamlakatimizni modernizatsiya qilish hamda hayotning barcha sohalarini liberallashtirish davlatimiz, fuqarolarimizning oliy maqsadi hisoblanadi. Terrorizm va ekstremizm bugungi kunda dunyo hamjamiyatini tashvishga solayotgan global muammolardan biri sifatida namoyon bo‘lib ulgurdi. Uning salbiy oqibatlari davlatlarning rivojlanishiga, fuqarolarning huquqlari, erkinliklari, qonuniy manfaatlarini to‘la taminlanishiga katta to‘siq bo‘lmoqda.

Prezidentimiz Sh.M.Mirziyoyev tomonidan 2022 – yil 28-yanvar kuni qabul

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qilingan “2022 – 2026 yillarga mo‘ljallangan Yangi O‘zbekistonning taraqqiyot strategiyasi to‘g‘risida” 60-sonli farmonning VI yo‘nalishida “Milliy manfaatlardan kelib chiqqan holda umumbashariy muammolarga yondashish” deb nomlangan VI yo‘nalishining 82-maqsadi aynan ekstremizm va terrorizmga bag‘ishlanadi. Xususan,

- Fuqarolarning huquq va erkinliklarini ta‘minlashga imkon beradigan ekstremizm va terrorizmga qarshi kurashish bo‘yicha samarali davlat siyosatini amalga oshirish;

- Ekstremizm va terrorizmni keltirib chiqaruvchi omillarning oldini olishga qaratilgan preventiv mexanizmlarni takomillashtirish, ijtimoiy-ma‘naviy muhitni yaxshilash, yot g‘oyalar ta‘sirini oldini olish va ularning ta‘siriga tushib qolganlar bilan tizimli ishlash orqali ularning muammolarini bartaraf etish;

- Aholi, ayniqsa yosh avlodda terrorizm va ekstremizm mafkurasiga qarshi qat‘iy va barqaror immunitetini shakllantirish;

- Ekstremizm va terrorizmga qarshi kurashishning xalqaro-huquqiy asoslarini takomillashtirish hamda xorijiy davlatlar, mintaqaviy va xalqaro tashkilotlar bilan ekstremizm va terrorizmga qarshi kurashish sohasidagi hamkorlikning shartnomaviy-huquqiy asoslarini kengaytirish;

- Diplomatik vakolatxonalar va konsullik muassasalari, Tashqi mehnat migratsiyasi agentligi, shuningdek, chet elga uzoq vaqtga ketayotgan hamda yashab kelayotgan fuqarolar bilan shug‘ullanuvchi boshqa idoralarning kadrlar salohiyati va resurslarini mustahkamlash;

- Xorijiy davlatlar va xalqaro tashkilotlar bilan ekstremizm, terrorizm va ularni moliyalashtirishga qarshi kurash sohasida axborot hamda tajriba almashish;

- Faoliyati ekstremizm va terrorizmga qarshi kurashishga qaratilgan xalqaro va mintaqaviy tashkilotlarda faol ishtirok etish;

- Markaziy Osiyoda BMTning Global aksilterror strategiyasini amalga oshirish

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bo'yicha hamkorlikdagi sa'y-harakatlarni birgalikdagi harakatlar rejasi doirasida muvofiqlashtirish;

- Markaziy Osiyoda ekstremizm va terrorizmga qarshi kurashish bo'yicha birgalikdagi ishlar doirasida axborot almashinuv va hamkorlikni rivojlantirishga yordam beruvchi xalqaro tashabbuslarni amalga oshirishda O'zbekistonning rolini kengaytirish;

- Dunyo hamjamiyati va mintaqaviy tashkilotlar e'tiborini Afg'onistonda tinchlik va hamjihatlikni ta'minlashga jalb qilish borasidagi tashabbuslarni jadallashtirish va ushbu mamlakatni mintaqaviy hamkorlik jarayonlariga, shu jumladan ekstremizm va terrorizmga qarshi kurashishga jalb qilish.

Fuqarolarning huquqlari, erkinliklari va qonuniy manfaatlarini himoya qilish, jamoat tartibini saqlash, shaxs, jamiyat va davlat xavfsizligini ta'minlash, huquqbuzarliklarning oldini olish va profilaktikasi bo'yicha respublikada yaxlit huquqiy tizim yaratilgan bo'lib, unda ichki ishlar organlari muhim o'rin egallaydi. O'tgan davr mobaynida ichki ishlar organlari tizimini takomillashtirish borasida keng ko'lamli ishlar amalga oshirildi. Ayniqsa, IIONing mahallalarda jamoat tartibini saqlash, fuqarolar xavfsizligini ta'minlash, huquqbuzarliklar profilaktikasi va jinoyatchilikka qarshi kurashish uchun tashkil etilgan quyi bo'g'inini rivojlantirish va mustahkamlash bo'yicha salmoqli ishlar amalga oshirildi. Amalga oshirilgan chora-tadbirlar ichki ishlar organlari faoliyatining samaradorligini oshirish fuqarolarning tinch va osoyishta hayot kechirishini ta'minlash, jinoyatchilik va huquqbuzarlikka qarshi kurashish, jamoat tartibini va xavfsizligini saqlash masalalari Prezidentimiz tomonidan olib borilayotgan davlat siyosatida eng muhim va ustuvor o'rin egallaydi hamda bu masala ichki ishlar tizimini tubdan isloh qilish, uning faoliyati samaradorligini zamonaviy bosqichga ko'tarishdek g'oyat murakkab vazifa doimiy ravishda kun tartibiga qo'yib kelinmoqda .

Jamiyatda tinchlik va osoyishtalikni saqlash, jamoat tartibi va xavfsizligini

ta'minlash, fuqarolarni huquq va erkinliklarini har qanday tajovuzlardan himoya qilishdek yuksak maqsadlarga erishish uchun istiqbol yillarida ichki ishlar organlari tizimini chuqur isloh qilish bo'yicha keng ko'lamli ishlar amalga oshirildi. Jumladan, har bir mahalla, eng olis, chekka qishloq ovullarimizgacha xalq bilan ishlaydigan uning dardu g'amiga hamdard, quvonch – tashvishiga sherik bo'lishga tayyor profilaktika inspektorlari faoliyat ko'rsatishiga imkoniyat yaratildi.

Jamiyat taraqqiyotining obyektiv qonuniyatlari va ularni taqazo etuvchi omillarning aloqadorlikda mamlakatdagi, uning ma'muriy hududlaridagi jamoat tartibi va xavfsizligiga ta'siri ularning mazmun – mohiyatidan kelib chiqib ijobiy va salbiy xususiyatga ega bo'lishi mumkin. Shuning uchun ichki ishlar organlari muntazam ravishda tizimli holda ushbu qonuniyatlarni va omillarni o'z vaqtida aniqlashlari, monitoring olib borishlari va uning natijalari bo'yicha:

a) Jamoat tartibi va xavfsizligiga ta'sir etuvchi omillardan ichki ishlar organlari ushbu jarayonni boshqarishda samarali foydalanishga;

b) Jamoat tartibi va xavfsizligiga ta'sir qiluvchi omillarni esa ichki ishlar organlari amaldagi qonun hujjatlarida belgilangan vakolatlar doirasida va tartibda bartaraf etish, zararsizlantirish choralari amalga oshirishlari talab qilinadi.

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ТРЕБОВАНИЕ ОСНОВНОЙ ПЛОЩАДКИ ЗЕМЛЯНОГО ПОЛОТНА ЖЕЛЕЗНЫХ ДОРОГ

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Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается важность и особенности конструирования земляного полотна железнодорожных путей с учетом требований к его устойчивости, несущей способности и деформируемости. Описывается структура основной площадки и обочины земляного полотна, методы обеспечения устойчивости, а также требования к грунтам, используемым при строительстве. Рассматриваются также геометрические параметры и конструктивные особенности земляного полотна в различных условиях, включая устройство насыпей, выемок и обработку слабых грунтов.

Abstract: This article discusses the importance and features of the construction of the railway trackbed, taking into account the requirements for its stability, load-bearing capacity and deformability. The structure of the main site and the roadside of the roadbed, methods of ensuring stability, as well as requirements for soils used in construction are described. The geometric parameters and design features of the roadbed are also considered in various conditions, including the construction of embankments, excavation and processing of weak soils.

Ключевые слова: деформация, морозное пучение, уплотнение грунта, защитный слой, насыпь, выемка, слабые грунты, эстакада, сваи, дренирование, конструкция.

Keywords: deformation, frost heaving, soil compaction, protective layer, embankment, excavation, weak soils, overpass, piles, drainage, construction.

Введение: Основной площадкой земляного полотна называется его верхняя поверхность, на которой размещается верхнее строение пути. Она

характеризуется формой поверхности (зависит от рода грунта и количества путей) и шириною b (зависит от категории линии, вида грунта, числа путей).

Обочинной земляного полотна называется часть основной площадки, свободная от балластной призмы. Обочина измеряется от подошвы балластной призмы до бровки земляного полотна, предназначена для обеспечения большей устойчивости откосных частей, а также удобства проведения путевых работ и размещения путевых знаков. На однопутных линиях поперечное очертание верха земляного полотна на перегонах имеет трапецеидальную форму высотой 0,15 м и шириной поверху 2,3 м, т.е. меньше длины шпалы, чтобы при укладке рельсошпальной решетки на основную площадку без балластирования не образовывались бы замкнутые углубления от вдавливания шпал в грунт.

На двухпутных линиях сливная призма имеет треугольную форму с высотой 0,20 м. Основная площадка земляного полотна из скальных и дренирующих грунтов принимается горизонтальной.

1-рисунок. Поперечное очертание основной площадки на прямых участках:

a - для однопутного земляного полотна из недренирующих грунтов без защитного слоя; *б* - то же из дренирующих грунтов; *в* - для двухпутного земляного полотна из недренирующих грунтов; *г* - то же из дренирующих грунтов; *b* - ширина основной площадки земляного полотна; *h* - 0,15 + разность толщин

балластного слоя на данном участке и смежных слоев из недренирующих грунтов; Бпроф - профильная бровка; Бп - проектная бровка

Особенность работы земляного полотна при скоростном движении пассажирских поездов заключается, с одной стороны, в необходимости полного недопущения его деформаций в уровне основной площадки, что определяется высокими нормами ровности содержания геометрии рельсовой колеи, а с другой стороны, повышенным вибродинамическим воздействием на грунты верхней части земляного полотна, возникающем при проходе поездов с высокими скоростями.

Эти особенности предъявляют повышенные требования к качеству

сооружаемого земляного полотна, ужесточению требований к используемым для отсыпки грунтам, повышению надежности и стабильности конструкций. В первую очередь данные требования относятся к рабочей зоне земляного полотна, воспринимающей вибродинамическое воздействие со стороны проходящих поездов.

Для основной площадки земляного полотна должны быть исключены деформации морозного пучения. В связи с этим верхняя часть земляного полотна на всю глубину промерзания должна состоять из непучинистых грунтов, что приводит к необходимости увеличения толщины защитного слоя больше глубины сезонного промерзания. Осадка земляного полотна должна полностью завершиться к моменту укладки верхнего строения пути, а норматив по упругой осадке в уровне основной площадки должен быть ужесточен до величины не более 1 мм.

Также более жесткие нормы принимаются к уплотнению грунтов защитного слоя и земляного полотна: верхний слой толщиной не менее 1,0 м должен иметь коэффициент уплотнения не ниже 1,0, а ниже лежащие слои не менее 0,98.

Устойчивость, несущая способность и деформируемость основания земляного полотна должны рассчитываться с учетом снижения прочностных и деформативных характеристик грунтов из-за вибродинамического воздействия с учетом его затухания. При этом устойчивость и несущая способность должна оцениваться по схемам предельного равновесия грунтового массива. Коэффициент общей устойчивости насыпей при расчетах по методу предельного равновесия грунтового массива (по круглоцилиндрической поверхности скольжения) должен быть не менее 1,25 под расчетной временной нагрузкой. Для сооружения насыпи допускаются грунты: скальные, крупнообломочные, песчаные, в летнее сухое время - глинистые твердой или полутвердой консистенции, кроме глинистых грунтов, характеризующихся влажностью на границе текучести $W_L > 0,40$, и песков со степенью неоднородности C_u менее 3,0 (однородные).

Защитный слой устраивается из двух слоев. Верхняя часть защитного слоя устраивается из щебенисто гравийно-песчаных смесей с заданным

гранулометрическим составом. Требуемый модуль деформации смеси в конструкции 60 МПа. Для нижнего защитного слоя допускается использовать: пески гравелистые, крупные и средней крупности, крупнообломочные грунты с песчаным заполнителем, отсева щебеночного производства. Модуль деформации грунтов в конструкции не менее 40 МПа.

Ширина основной площадки двухпутного земляного полотна (на прямой) определяется следующими геометрическими параметрами.

Величина междупутья между главными путями -4,50 м, величина обочин - 0,90 м, плечо балластной призмы-0,50 м, Крутизна откосов балластной призмы -1:1,5; Толщина щебня под шпалой - 0,40 м

Насыпи ниже защитного слоя на сыром и мокром основании следует проектировать из дренирующих грунтов. На подходной части насыпи к искусственному сооружению проектируют сопряжения путем устройства участков переменной жесткости протяжением не менее 30 м. При небольшой высоте насыпей на косогорах, а также на участках полувыемок и полунасыпей для исключения неравномерного деформирования следует с помощью замены грунтов обеспечивать однородные грунтовые условия под основной площадкой.

Слабые грунты в основании насыпей толщиной слоя до 3,0 м следует удалять. При невозможности удаления слабых грунтов или при соответствующем технико - экономическом обосновании насыпи могут сооружаться с сохранением слабых грунтов. В конструкции насыпей, сооружаемых с сохранением слабых грунтов, по результатам расчетов могут быть предусмотрены мероприятия по упрочнению основания, снижению величины или выравниванию его осадки вдоль и поперек пути (грунтовые или железобетонные сваи, геосинтетические материалы, вертикальное дренирование, замена земляного полотна на эстакаду и т.п.). Насыпи на болотах сооружаются с полным удалением торфа из основания. При большой (более 3,0-4,0 м) толщине слоя торфа насыпи сооружаются на свайном основании или земляное полотно (как конструкция) подлежит замене на эстакаду.

Конструкцию выемок следует проектировать в зависимости от их

глубины, видов и свойств грунтов, климатических условий района строительства, с учетом способа производства работ. Толщина защитного слоя, как и на насыпях, принимается из условия полного выведения пучинистых грунтов из зоны сезонного промерзания. В выемках и нулевых местах должен быть осуществлен отвод воды от подошвы (низа) защитного слоя. При плотности глинистых грунтов под защитным слоем менее $0,95\rho_{d_{max}}$ предусматриваются мероприятия:

- уплотнение грунтов основания;
- увеличение (по расчету) толщины защитного слоя;
- упрочнение грунтов добавками, армированием и т.п.

Вывод: Так, на длительно эксплуатируемых линиях за основную площадку принимается условная граница, проходящая по подошве балластной призмы типовых размеров. При этом балластная призма, создаваемая в ходе ремонтов пути, является однослойной и в ней нормируется толщина щебня под шпалой и плечо в зависимости от класса пути.

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**Multi spiral Computed Tomography Analysis of Chronic Lung Disease
Complications in Patients Who Have Undergone Covid-19 Pneumonia**

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ABSTRACT

The article provides an analysis of changes in the pulmonary parenchyma in pneumonia caused by a new coronavirus infection in the acute and separated period of the course of the disease. Based on clinical material (60 patients with viral pneumonia, who underwent classical lung radiography and computed tomography at various times of the disease) changes in radiological signs of lung tissue damage were assessed. The dependence of the course and regression of the disease on the degree of lung tissue damage was revealed according to the results of radiography and computed tomography

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Keywords: Coronavirus infection, viral pneumonia, radiography, computer tomography, «frosted glass», fibrosis

During the pandemic of a new coronavirus infection, the question of the possible consequences of the infection, the assessment of post-inflammatory changes and quality of life is widely discussed in clinical practice. As of November 14, 2021, according to the World Health Organization website, 254 million cases of the new coronavirus infection COVID-19 were registered, of which 5.1 million were fatal, 229.1 million patients recovered. Among the complications of infection caused by SARS-CoV-2, complications associated with damage to the lungs, heart and blood vessels, kidneys and central nervous system are distinguished [1, 2]. Among domestic and foreign publications, there are isolated works devoted to the long-term results of COVID-19 treatment [3].

The purpose of the study. To evaluate the features of the course of the inflammatory process, to study the condition of the lung tissue according to the results of multisection computed tomography (MSCT) 1, 3 and 6

months after completion of treatment in patients with COVID-19-associated pneumonia.

Material and methods. The Main Military Clinical Hospital of the National Guard Troops of the Russian Federation analyzed the results of examination and treatment of 60 patients (41 (68%) men and 19 (32%) women) aged 37 to 81 years (average

age – 52.5 ± 5.1 years) who were treated in the period from March 2020 to March 2021 about viral pneumonia caused by COVID-

19. The data obtained using classical radiography, MSCT of patients with varying degrees of severity of lung tissue damage, at admission, after 1, 3 and 6 months were analyzed. Depending on the degree of lung tissue damage, the patients were divided into four groups of 15 people each: with minimal damage according to computed tomography (CT-1), with mild damage (CT-2), moderate (CT- 3) and severe damage (CT-4). The criteria for inclusion in the study were the presence of clinical signs of COVID-19 viral pneumonia, the identification of changes in the lungs

characteristic of this disease using radiation diagnostics methods and positive results of reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction on SARSCoV-2. The exclusion criteria were the presence of bacterial pneumonia and other acute diseases of the upper respiratory tract. The main method of assessing the state of the pulmonary parenchyma after a new coronavirus infection was multi-slice computed tomography (MSCT) performed on a 16-slice computed tomograph Toshiba Aquilion (Japan); 128-slice computed tomograph Philips (Netherlands); 64-slice computed tomograph Siemens Go Top (Germany).

The severity of pneumonia was assessed on the basis of criteria approved by the order of the Moscow Department of Health of 08.04.2020 No. 373 and the order of 16.04.2020 No. 10-18-231/20. The degree of damage to the lung tissue was assessed by the volume of involvement of its parenchyma: does not correspond to pneumonia – CT-0, minimal – CT- 1 (less than 25%), mild – CT-2 (25-50%), moderate – CT-3 (50-75%) or severe – CT-4 (75- 100%) [1]. Laboratory diagnostics of COVID-19 was carried out by reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction. The material from the patient's oropharynx was examined. The study was conducted in the

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laboratories of Rospotrebnadzor and the Main Center for State Sanitary and Epidemiological Surveillance of the National Guard Troops of the Russian Federation. Statistical processing of the obtained results was carried out using the Microsoft Office 2016 software package.

The results of the study. The analysis of the obtained results made it possible to identify criteria for residual phenomena in the form of the presence of a "frosted glass" symptom, with unilateral (1A) and bilateral (2A) localization, as well as local pneumofibrosis of lung tissue with unilateral (1B) and bilateral (2B) localization.

Discussion Taking into account the clinical course of lung tissue damage in patients who have had SARS and MERS, a group of doctors from the University of California strongly recommends monitoring patients who have had COVID-19 and checking their lungs "to assess long-term or permanent damage,

including fibrosis" [3, 4]. In our study, lung MSCT performed 1 month after discharge from the hospital showed that in 100% of cases, patients with CT2–4 retained residual changes in the lungs in the form of compaction of lung tissue by the type of "frosted glass", "cobblestone pavement", reticular pattern. In patients with CT-1, in 87% of cases, only residual compaction of the lung tissue by the type of "frosted glass" was preserved [1, 3, 5]. Studies conducted after 3 and 6 months demonstrated polymorphism and dynamism of the above–described patterns in patients with CT2-4, which were completely leveled after 6 months in patients with CT2–3. In patients with CT-4, after 6 months, both unilateral and bilateral fibrotic lung changes were detected in 14% of cases (Fig. 1). In 72% of cases, patients with changes characteristic of CT-4 had complete regression. In two cases, fibrous changes were detected, however, after a retrospective review of studies, including

classical X-ray images, these areas of lung tissue compaction were characterized as zones of local fibrosis and were classified as "without fibrous changes".

Conclusions.

1. The absence of long-term changes on the part of the lung tissue in severe pneumonia caused by COVID-19 in 72% of cases may indicate an atypical course of inflammation in its classical sense, requiring further study.
2. In 28% of patients with CT-4, 1, 3 and 6 months after COVID-19, post-inflammatory changes persist in the form of local one- or two- sided pneumofibrosis, which may be both a consequence of the addition of bacterial flora and a complication of the course of interstitial viral pneumonia (pneumonitis).
3. The detection of long-term changes in the lungs after 1, 3 and 6 months makes it necessary for such patients to carry out a complex of diagnostic and therapeutic and preventive measures for at least 6 months after the regression of clinical and laboratory signs of COVID-19.

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Ilova konstruksiyada hol bilan ifodalangan ilovali elementlar haqida

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ilova konstruksiyalarning o‘rganilishi, sintaktik aloqalarning shakllanishi, ilovali elementlarning ikkinchi darajali bo‘laklar, xususan, hol bilan ifodalanishi haqida so‘z boradi. Bu ilova konstruksiyalarning struktur-semantik xususiyatlari nemis badiiy adabiyotidan olingan matnlar–misollarning tahlili asosida ochib berilgan. Ushbu jarayonda mazkur sohada tadqiqot ishlarini olib borgan olimlarning ilmiy-nazariy xulosalaridan unumli foydalanilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: ilovali element, ilova hodisasi, ilova konstruksiyasi, struktur-semantik, sintaktik aloqalar, intonatsiya, badiiy asar, qo‘shimcha ma’no, asosiy ifoda, ikkinchi darajali bo‘lak-hol, bosh bo‘laklar, ma’lum bo‘lak.

Tilshunoslikda ilova hodisasi, ilovali konstruksiyalarni o‘rganish nazariy jihatdan ham, amaliy jihatdan ham katta ahamiyatga ega. Ilova hodisasini, ilova konstruksiyalarni tadqiq qilish juda ko‘plab tilshunos olimlarning diqqat-e’tiborini

o'ziga jalb qilgan muammodir. Ilovali konstruksiyalar masalasi turli tillarda ham strukturaviy, ham semantik va stilistik tomondan o'rganilib, har xil talqin qilinmoqda.

Ta'kidlash lozimki, ilovali konstruksiya - bu birinchi navbatda, stilistik xususiyatga ega bo'gan tuzilma.

Shuning uchun ham ko'pincha tilshunos olimlar, uning aynan shu jihatini ko'proq o'rganib, bu konstruksiyaning strukturaviy va semantik xususiyatini chetda qoldirmoqda.

Taniqli tilshunos olim O.P. Jdanova o'zining "Sintaktik munosabatlar qatorida ilova aloqalarning o'rni haqida" nomli maqolasida quyidagi ta'rifni keltiradi: Shunday qilib, ilova konstruksiyalar deb shunday strukturaviy tuzilmani aytishimiz mumkinki, u yerda asosiy ifoda (gap)ga sintaktik va kommunikativ jihatdan mustaqil bo'lmagan qism (bo'lak) qo'shimcha (ilova) qilinadi, bu qism gapning tarkibiga qarab to'ldiruvchi, hol yoki murakkablashgan konstruksiya bo'lib kelishi mumkin.

Shu o'rinda mazkur sohada quyidagilarni ta'kidlash lozim: "ba'zi hollarda asosiy ifoda bilan ilovali elementlar o'rtasidagi sintaktik aloqalar biriktiruvchi vositalarsiz, ya'ni intonatsiya(ohang) yo'li bilan amalga oshirilishi mumkin. Bunday holatda ilovali konstruksiyalar tarkibidagi ilovali elementlar biriktirivchi vositalarsiz birikkan gap shaklida bo'ladi [3; 58]."

Yuqorida bildirilgan fikr-mulohazalarni tahlil qilib, ularga tayangan holda quyidagilarni qo'shimcha qilish mumkin: "Biroq mazmunan bu kabi ilovali elementlar asosiy ifoda bilan birgalikda o'zaro yaxlit bir umumiy fikrni anglatishga qaratilgan bo'ladi va ilovali element talaffuzda tekis intonatsiya bilan aytiladi [2; 110]."

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Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, xuddi ana shunday xususiyatlar bu yerda tahlilga tortiladigan ikkinchi darajali bo'lak, xususan, hol shaklida ifodalanib keluvchi ilovali konstruksiyalarda ham namoyon bo'ladi.

Bunday ilova konstruksiyalarning strukturaviy va semantik xususiyatlarini o'rganishda va ularni tahlil qilishda hozirgi zamon nemis yozuvchilarining badiiy asarlaridan to'plangan misollarga tayanib, ish olib borish lozim.

Biz tomondan olib borilgan izlanishlar va kuzatuvlar hozirgi zamon nemis tili adabiy tilida hol shaklida ifodalanib keluvchi ilova konstruksiyalarning yoyilish darajasi ancha yuqori ekanligi va ularning strukturaviy jihatdan xilma-xilligini tasdiqlamoqda.

Badiiy matndan olingan misollar tahlili shuni ko'rsatadiki, hol ham ilovali konstruksiya tarkibida o'rin-joy, yo'nalish, payt, miqdor-daraja kabi ma'no xususiyatlarini bildirib, asosiy gap tarkibidagi ma'lum bir bo'lakning mazmunini to'ldirib, aniqlashtirib, izohlab kelishi mumkin:

1. Gisela blättert die Seiten im Block zurück, langsam nach den anderen. In ihrem Zimmer [Flegel Walter 1976 : 185].

Yuqoridagi keltirilgan misoldagi „In ihrem Zimmer“ ilovali elementi

asosiy ifodada ostiga chizilgan gap bo'lagiga ma'lum aniqlik kiritish, uni to'ldirish, ularga qo'shimcha ma'no berish uchun yuzaga kelgan. Ushbu fikr bilan shu narsani tasdiqlash va ta'kidlash mumkinki, ilovali elementlar faqatgina asosiy ifoda ham strukturaviy, ham semantik tomonidan mustaqil ma'no xususiyatiga ega bo'lganida yugaza keladi va turli shakllarda namoyon bo'ladi.

Buning sababi shuki, bu ikkala ilovali elementni gap tarkibidan chiqarib tashlasak, asosiy ifoda(gap) oddiy murakkab ergashgan qo'shma gap shakliga ega bo'lib qoladi.

2. Aber sie werden sich in den Abteilungen versammeln und eine Erklärung beraten. Auch in dieser Gruppe [Herbert Otto 1972 : 5].

Ushbu misoldagi ilovali element asosiy ifodaning tarkibida kelgan „in dieser Gruppe“ so‘z birikmasiga qisman aniqlik kiritish bilan takrorlanib kelgan.

3. In ganz Shanghai wird, wie mir berichtet wurde, unter der Hand mit Blut spekuliert. In der Abteilungen der Armee auch [Bredel Willi 1981 : 373].

Voqea-hodisaning sodir bo‘lish o‘rnini ifodalash shaklida kelgan bu ilovali elementning asosiy vazifasi, asosiy ifodada ish harakatning qayerda sodir bo‘lishini ko‘rsatib, uning biror bo‘lagini aniqlab to‘ldirib keladi[3 : 58].

Shunday qilib, ilova konstruksiya tarkibidagi ilovali elementlar hol shaklida ifodalanib kelganda asosiy ifoda bilan ilovali element orasidagi sintaktik aloqalar, gapdagi bosh va ikkinchi darajali bo‘laklarning ishtiroki asosida amalga oshadi. Bunda murakkab sintaktik butunlik komponentlarining bo‘lishi asosiy ifoda bilan ilovali elementlar o‘rtasidagi sintaktik aloqalarni o‘rganishda muhim rol o‘ynaydi. Demak, ilovali element aynan shu holatlar asosida yuzaga keladi.

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O'tkir osti tireoidit ni qiyosiy tashxislash

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Annotatsiya: Tiroidit – o'tkir, o'tkir osti, surunkali, autoimmun xarakterdagi qalqonsimon bezning yallig'lanishli shikastlanishi. Bosim hissi, bo'yin og'rig'i, yutish qiyinligi, ovoz balandligi bilan namoyon bo'ladi. O'tkir yallig'lanishda abses shakllanishi mumkin. Ushbu maqola o'tkir osti tireoidit ni qiyosiy tashxislash haqida yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Tiroidit, tashxislash, davolash, alomatlar, o'tkir osti.

Абстрактный: Тиреоидит – острое, подострое, хроническое, аутоиммунное воспалительное поражение щитовидной железы. Проявляется ощущением давления, болью в шее, затруднением глотания, повышением громкости голоса. Абсцесс может образоваться при остром воспалении. В статье рассмотрена сравнительная диагностика острого субтиреоидита.

Ключевые слова: Тиреоидит, диагностика, лечение, симптомы, подострое течение.

Abstract: Thyroiditis is an acute, subacute, chronic, autoimmune inflammatory lesion of the thyroid gland. It manifests itself as a feeling of pressure, pain in the neck, difficulty swallowing, and increased voice volume. An abscess can form during acute inflammation. The article discusses the comparative diagnosis of acute subthyroiditis.

Key words: Thyroiditis, diagnosis, treatment, symptoms, subacute course.

Kasallikning rivojlanishi bezdagi diffuz o'zgarishlarga va uning funktsiyalarining buzilishiga olib keladi: birinchi navbatda, gipertiroidizm hodisalari, keyin esa – tegishli davolanishni talab qiladigan gipotiroidizm. Klinik belgilari va kechishiga qarab, o'tkir, o'tkit osti va surunkali tiroidit farqlanadi; etiologiyasi bo'yicha – autoimmun, sifilitik, sil kasalligi va boshqalar.

Umumiy ma'lumot

Tiroidit – o'tkir, o'tkir osti, surunkali, autoimmun xarakterdagi qalqonsimon bezning yallig'lanishli shikastlanishi. Bosim hissi, bo'yin og'rig'i, yutish qiyinligi, ovoz balandligi bilan namoyon bo'ladi. O'tkir yallig'lanishda abses shakllanishi mumkin. Kasallikning rivojlanishi bezdagi diffuz o'zgarishlarga va uning funktsiyalarining buzilishiga olib keladi: birinchi navbatda, gipertiroidizm hodisalari, keyin esa – tegishli davolanishni talab qiladigan gipotiroidizm.

Tiroidit turli mexanizm va paydo bo'lish sabablariga asoslangan bo'lishi mumkin, ammo kasalliklarning butun guruhi qalqonsimon bez to'qimalariga ta'sir qiluvchi yallig'lanish komponentining mavjudligi bilan birlashtirilgan.

Tiroidit klassifikatsiyasi

Klinik endokrinologiya o'z amaliyotida ularning rivojlanish mexanizmining o'ziga xos xususiyatlariga va klinik ko'rinishlariga asoslangan tiroiditning tasnifini qo'llaydi. Tiroiditning quyidagi shakllari mavjud: o'tkir, o'tkir osti va surunkali.

O'tkir tiroidit butun bo'lakka yoki butun qalqonsimon bezga tarqalishi mumkin (diffuz) yoki bez bo'lakning qisman shikastlanishi (fokal) bilan davom etishi mumkin. Bundan tashqari, o'tkir tiroiditda yallig'lanish yiringli yoki yiringsiz bo'lishi mumkin.

O'tkir osti tiroidit uchta klinik ko'rinishda uchraydi: granulomatoz, pnevmokista va limfotsitar tiroidit; Tarqalishi fokusli va tarqoq. Surunkali tiroidit guruhi Hashimoto ning autoimmun tiroiditi, Riedelning fibroz-invaziv buqog'i va tuberkulyoz, sifilitik va septomikoz etiologiyali o'ziga xos tiroiditi bilan ifodalanadi. O'tkir tiroiditning yiringli shakli va Riedelning surunkali fibro-invaziv buqog'i juda kam uchraydi.

Tiroidit sabablari

O'tkir yiringli tiroiditning rivojlanishi o'tkir yoki surunkali yuqumli kasalliklar – tonzillit, pnevmoniya, sepsis va boshqalardan so'ng, ularning patogenlarini qalqonsimon bez to'qimalariga gematogen tarzda kirishi natijasida yuzaga keladi. Tiroiditning o'tkir yiringli bo'lmagan shakli qalqonsimon bezning shikastlanishi, radiatsiyaviy shikastlanishi natijasida, shuningdek, uning to'qimalarida qon ketishidan keyin rivojlanishi mumkin.

O'tkir osti (granulomatoz) Kerven tiroiditi turli infeksiyalarning patogenlari: adenoviruslar, qizamiq viruslari, gripp, parotit tomonidan qalqonsimon bez hujayralariga virusli zarar yetkazishga asoslangan. Kasallik 5-6 baravar tez-tez rivojlanadi, asosan 20 yoshdan 50 yoshgacha bo'lgan ayollarda, virusli infeksiya natijasidan bir necha hafta yoki oy o'tgach klinik namoyon bo'ladi. Kerven tiroiditi epidemiyasi eng katta virusli faollik davrlari bilan bog'liq. O'tkir osti tiroidit autoimmunga qaraganda 10 baravar kamroq rivojlanadi va qalqonsimon bezning qaytariladigan, vaqtinchalik disfunktsiyasi bilan birga keladi. Nazofarenksning

surunkali infeksiyalari va irsiy omillar o'tkir osti tiroiditning rivojlanishiga sabab bo'ladi.

Fibroz tiroidit (Ridel buqog'i) bilan qalqonsimon bezdagi biriktiruvchi to'qimalarning sezilarli darajada ko'payishi va bo'yin tuzilmalarining siqilishi mavjud. Ridel buqog'ining rivojlanishi 40-50 yoshdan oshgan ayollarda tez-tez uchraydi. Fibroz tiroiditning etiologiyasi oxirigacha aniqlanmagan: uning rivojlanishida infeksiyalarning ma'lum roli taxmin qilinadi, ba'zi tadqiqotchilar Ridelning buqog'ini Hashimoto tiroiditida qalqonsimon bezning autoimmun zararlanishining natijasi deb hisoblashadi. Fibroz tiroiditning rivojlanishi tirotoksikoz, qalqonsimon bez jarrohligi, endemik buqoq, genetik moyillik, shuningdek, autoimmun va allergik kasalliklar, qandli diabet bilan og'rikan bemorlarga moyil bo'ladi.

Tireoidit belgilari

O'tkir tireoidit

O'tkir tiroiditning yiringli shaklida qalqonsimon bezning yallig'lanish infiltratsiyasi kuzatiladi, so'ngra unda abses (yiring) hosil bo'ladi. Yiringli sintez zonasi sekretor faollikdan o'chiriladi, lekin ko'pincha u bez to'qimalarining ahamiyatsiz qismini egallaydi va gormonal sekretiyaning keskin buzilishiga olib kelmaydi.

Yiringli tiroidit o'tkir rivojlanadi – yuqori harorat (40 ° C gacha) va titroq bilan kechadi. Bo'yinning old yuzasida boshning, jag'ning, tilning, quloqning orqa tomoniga siljish bilan o'tkir og'riqlar bo'ladi, yo'talish, yutish va bosh harakati bilan kuchayadi. Intoksikatsiya tez sur'atlar bilan o'sib boradi: kuchli holsizlik, charchoq, mushaklar va bo'g'imlarning og'rig'i, bosh og'rig'i va taxikardiya kuchayadi. Ko'pincha bemorning ahvoli og'ir deb baholanadi.

Palpatsiya qalqonsimon bezning mahalliy yoki diffuz kengayishi, qattiq og'riq, zich (infiltrativ yallig'lanish bosqichida) yoki yumshoq (yiringli sintez va abses shakllanishi bosqichida) mustahkamlik bilan aniqlanadi. Bo'yin terisining giperemiyasi, haroratning mahalliy ko'tarilishi, bo'yin limfa tugunlarining ko'payishi va og'rig'i bo'ladi. O'tkir tiroiditning yiringli bo'lmagan shakli qalqonsimon bez to'qimalarining aseptik yallig'lanishi bilan tavsiflanadi va kamroq og'ir belgilar bilan davom etadi.

Tiroiditni davolash

Tiroiditning yengil shakllarida endokrinologning kuzatuvi, og'riqni yo'qotish uchun steroid bo'lmagan yallig'lanishga qarshi dorilarni tayinlash va simptomatik terapiya bilan cheklanishi mumkin. Jiddiy diffuz yallig'lanish bilan steroid gormonlar qo'llaniladi (dozani bosqichma-bosqich kamaytirish bilan prednizolon).

O'tkir yiringli tiroiditda bemor jarrohlik bo'limiga yotqiziladi. Faol antibakterial terapiya (penitsillinlar, sefalosporinlar), B va C vitaminlari, antigistaminlar (mebidrolin, xloropiramin, klemastin, siprogeptadin), massiv vena ichiga detoksifikatsiya terapiyasi (tuzli eritmalar, reopoliglyukin) buyuriladi. Qalqonsimon bezda abses hosil bo'lganda, u jarrohlik yo'li bilan ochiladi va drenajlanadi.

O'tkir osti va surunkali tiroiditni davolash tiroid gormonlari bilan amalga oshiriladi. Bo'yinning tuzilmalarini siqish belgilari bilan siqilish sindromi rivojlanishi bilan ular jarrohlik aralashuvga murojaat qilishadi. Maxsus tiroidit asosiy kasallikni davolash orqali davolanadi.

Prognoz va profilaktika

O'tkir tiroiditni erta davolash bemorning 1,5-2 oy ichida to'liq tiklanishi bilan yakunlanadi. Kamdan kam hollarda, yiringli tiroiditdan keyin doimiy gipotiroidizm

rivojlanishi mumkin. O'tkir osti tiroiditning faol terapiyasi 2-3 oy ichida davolanishga erishishi mumkin. Uzoq davom etgan o'tkir osti shakllari 2 yilgacha davom etishi va surunkali bo'lishi mumkin. Fibroz tiroidit hipotiroidizmning uzoq muddatli rivojlanishi bilan tavsiflanadi.

Tiroiditning oldini olish uchun yuqumli va virusli kasalliklarning oldini olishning roli katta: qattiqlashuv, vitamin terapiyasi, sog'lom ovqatlanish va turmush tarzi. Surunkali infeksiya o'choqlarini o'z vaqtida reabilitatsiya qilish kerak: karies, otit, tonzillit, sinusit, pnevmoniya va boshqalarni davolash. Tibbiy tavsiyalar va retseptlarni bajarish, gormonlar dozasini o'z-o'zidan kamaytirish yoki ularni bekor qilishning oldini olish yordam beradi.

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